

Documentation of Karnāṭaka Christian compositions of H. A. Popley: A Study

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Abstract

Expressing devotion through music is a common phenomenon in almost all religions in the world. The Christian community of South India has embraced Karnāṭaka Music as one of the ways of practicing religious music. This has created a scope for new compositions consisting elements of classical music with Christian themes and lyrics. The compositional works of one of the Christian composers and lyricists, H. A. Popley has been analyzed in this paper focusing on the style of the documentation of his musical compositions as well as his contribution in Christian culture by making use of Karnāṭaka Music. The compositions as well as the commentary-based literature on Popley's work are aimed to be studied in this paper. The connection between the Christian community and Karnāṭaka classical music in general is also to be studied to substantiate the conclusion about the impact of the documentation of H. A. Popley's Christian Karnāṭaka Music on modern day practices in the community.

Keywords: H. A. Popley, Christian Compositions, Karnataka Music, Documentation

Documentation of Christian Kirtana – The Background Study

Karnāṭaka music with its complex rhythmic patterns, intricate melodies, and the improvisational elements that are central to the performance, has historically been practiced in Hindu temples and Courts. The Christian community in India has embraced Karnāṭaka music as a way to incorporate their faith into their musical tradition. This has led to the creation of a distinct style of Christian Karnāṭaka music that combines elements of the classical tradition with Christian themes and lyrics. The pioneers or the forefathers of

Christian Karnāṭaka music, paved the way for the vast world of music through their valuable compositions and their exemplary life. It is remarkable that a number of foreign personalities had imprinted their foot-prints in the field of Karnāṭaka music to popularize it on a national and international level. All the compositions of the composer need systematic documentation. Some of the compositions are documented which are well reflected in existing publications. However, documenting and archiving the musical works of the composer can further be done.

Methodology and Limitation

Four compositions are purposely selected as samples for analysis of the notations and lyrics and to make comparison of the songs with original Karnāṭaka kirtans. The practices of music in the church have been observed and existing literature has been studied to understand the modern-day practices in the community.

The Music Research Library, Google Scholar etc. are used as databases for collecting published materials. One of the Christian composers and lyricists, H. A. Popley has been analyzed in this paper. Among the four tune books, two books are available online. Selected compositions mainly focusing on the style of the documentation of his musical compositions as well as the gaps has been mentioned.

Objectives

1. To find out the documentation technique of the compositions in regards to the notation system.
2. To find out the nature of the compositions (lyrics and music) that impacted the Christian community
3. To find out gaps in documentation that can be filled with academic ideas or modern techniques of preservation.

About H. A. Popley

H. A. Popley (1868-1960) was a Christian missionary who lived in India from 1902 till his death. He had a strong interest in both traditional music and Tamil literature. Inspired by Hindu devotional practices in Tamil, he was a pioneer in musical evangelism, adopting traditional music and using it to illustrate his Christian beliefs. He has handled the most popular Janaka and Janyarāga-s and mostly set in the form of Gītam, and Svarajati. And he has made use of the common rhythms (*Tāla-s*). Popley initiated new steps for the culturalization in the field of Karnāṭaka Music. He was well-known for his literary work as a translator of the Thirukural and his skill in rendering Tamil Christian music in the Karnāṭaka style. His contributions lead many to seek further light on this most interesting part of the wonderful Heritage of India through his book ‘The Music of India’. He openly showed his support for Indian Nationalism as well. He lived in India from 1902 till his death.¹

Literary work of H. A. Popley:

H. A. Popley has written various works in the field of literature apart from devotional and musical skills. He Published on a variety of topics such as history, education, London mission work, music, social organization etc. “**The Music of India**”² is a Popular book around the world. It contains a deep understanding of the Heritage of India. The book aims to give light to the musical heritage of India and make the information available to ‘the educated Indian and also the European’ for them to grow interest in Indian Music.

The book contains descriptions of Hindustani and Karnatik Music Traditions, Historical background from Vedic period and the development of Indian Music. Explanation about the development of scale, Tala, Musical Compositions, different ragas with the use of

¹ "Leaders, Christian." Encyclopedia of India. . Encyclopedia.com. 21 Feb. 2024 <https://www.encyclopedia.com>

² H. A. Popley. The Music of India. Calcutta: Association press, 1921.

Staff notation, different musical instruments of India, the book concludes with discussion on the Indian and western music system.

Another book by H. A. Popley is “**The Sacred Kural**”³, published in 1931. Tamil literature is one of the few regional literatures of India, which in the early centuries of the Christian era, attained to a high development and standard, which bear comparison with Sanskrit literature. The Kural is one of the most important forms of classical Tamil poetry. Popley was well known for his translation of “Kural” and his skill in rendering Tamil Christian music in the Karnāṭaka style which is reflected in this book.

Documentation technique of the composition:

The Indian notation system is complex in terms of Svara and rhythm patterns in it. Popley’s songs are published in staff notation which makes them understandable to musicians from non-Indian musical background. However, Popley opined that “any strict adherence to English tonic solfa signs is quite impossible”⁴ to render Indian or Carnatic compositions with accuracy of compositions. The composer understood that using western system may not bring the perfection of the original idea or melody, but western system is less complex and thus, can be easily decoded. The Table of Time signs from the book “Handbook of Musical Evangelism” by L I Stephen and H. A. Popley to document Indian melody is given below;

Time signs	Explanations
	The long thick upright strokes indicate the bars.
	The shorter upright strokes in between indicate the divisions of the bar into beats.

³ H A Popley, The Sacred Kural, or the Tamil Veda of Tiruvalluvar. New Delhi: Abhijeet Publication, 1931.

⁴ Stephen L.I. and Popley H.A., Handbook of Musical Evangelism. Madras: Methodist publishing house, 1914.

: : :	Two dots placed one above another indicate co-equal time member within the beat
. . . .	Single dots between the above indicate co-equal divisions of the time member.
„	The comma placed after the dot indicates that the preceding division is extended by one half, the previous note taking up half the time of the next note.e. g.: d n., ś :
Fin	Indicates that the music must end at this point.
R	Placed above a note indicates that the portion preceding must be repeated at this point, from the point where another similar sign occurs
_	In a space indicates the lengthening of the preceding note for the space or spaces occupied by the dash.
: :	An empty space indicates a rest when no note is sounded.
_____	A line under two or more notes denotes that the notes must be sung in one breath and elided together.
^	Placed over a note indicates that a pause must be made at this note which should be lengthened beyond the time allotted.
!	Placed over a note indicates that the note should be played sharply and with emphasis, disconnected from the other notes. It is the staccato of western music.
⋮	Two dots with a third dot between indicates that a subsidiary beat occurs at that place. This only occurs in Misra Eka Tala

The Nature of the compositions (Lyrics and Music)

1. *Yēsu nāmam onrainampuvīr - Rāga: Khamās - Tāla: Ādi - Tonic Note: C*

The notation given by the composer in western system⁵ is given below

131. ஏசு நாமம் ஒன்றை நம்புவீர்

Khamās. *Ādi.*

Tonic C. Fin. D. C.

Pal. | மா நீ தா தா பா மா கா | மா ; ; கா | மா பா தா நீ ||
ஏசு நாமம் ஒன்றை நம்புவீர் பூலோகத் தாரே

Cha. | மா நீ தா நீ சாசா சாசா | நீ தா நீ சா | ச்சீ நீ தாபா |
ஏசு நாமம் ஒன்றை நம்பும் ரட்சண் யத்துக் கிதுவே ஸ்தம்பம்

D. C.

| நீ சா நீ சா நீ தா நீ சா | சா நீ தாபா | மாகா மபநீ ||
பேசும் வேறே நாமம் எல்லாம் பேரு லகை ரட்சிக் காதே

Meaning:

Jesus is the only savior. The world ought to embrace the name of Christ, for those who believe in His name, shall find salvation. No other name can grant salvation, only Jesus' name.

Musical aspect

This song is composed in Khamās rāga and set in Ādi tāla. The melody of the song is closely similar to the popular Svarajati “Sāmba Śiva...”. Both the pallavi-s begin with the svara tāra ṣaḍja. The song begins with jaṅṭa prayōga in the svara ‘ś’, but the traditional

⁵ Popley, H A, “Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 2, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz),” *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,

svarajati consist only one svāra ś and kārvaī-s. Each svāra contains two counts “ś,ś,n,d,p,m,g,” and use jaṅṭa prayōga-s in svāra-s ‘ś’ and ‘d’. The ending note ‘m’ adds more beauty for this song. The svāra ‘m’ contains six counts and oscillates with the sound ‘p’. So, the pañcama is the anuswara for this phrase. Then melody goes to the ‘g’ and followed in ārōhaṇa krama and ends with ‘n’.

SONG	T	1	2	3	T	V	T	V
Yēsunāmam	ś , ś ,	n , d ,	d , p ,	m , g ,	m , , ,	, , g ,	m , p ,	d , n ,
Sāmbaśiva	ś , , ,	, , n ,	d , p ,	, m g ,	m , , ,	, , g ,	m , p ,	d , n ,

The carāṇa begins with the note ‘m’. The viśēṣaprayōga like “m,n,d,n, ndnś” are used in this composition. The Svāra Niṣādama has been used in two different varieties. First, Niṣādama oscillates with ‘d’ and in the second niṣādama oscillates with tāra ṣaḍja. Then comes the note tāra ṣaḍja for the next two akṣarakāla “ś,ś,ś,ś,”. Each ‘ś’ should be stressed.

Jaṅṭa prayōga is used in tāra ṣaḍja. The charana of the song is totally different from the svarajati, and the song proceeds by the phrase “n,ś,ś,ś,n,d,n,ś,”. Each note comes on the beat and svāra-s ‘n’, ‘r’, ‘n’, ‘n’ have more stress than the other svāras. And followed by the phrase “ś,n,d,p,m,g,” in ārōhaṇa krama in the same count till the end with the phrase “mpdn”. The song ends in ‘n’. The range of the song is madhya sthāyi gāndhāra to tāra sthāyi riṣabam.

2. *Anaivarum Pāḍiuvōm - Rāga: Bilahari - Tāla: Ādi - Tonic Note: C*

The notation given by the composer in western system⁶ is illustrated below

Meaning

We will sing with joyful hearts, grateful for the Omnipotent protection up to this moment.

Musical aspect

This song is in Bilahari rāga and set to Ādi tāla. Popely chose the melody of the Bilahari svarajati “Rā ra vēṇu gōpābāla” for this song. The song commences with the note ‘s’ and melody progresses in the ārōhaṇa krama of Bilahari rāga so that it is easy to identify. and ends in madhya sthāyi ‘s’.

The first line of both songs is mentioned below.

SONG	T	1	2	3	T	V	T	V
Anaivarum	s , , r	g , p ,	d , ś ,	n , d ,	pp d p	m g r s	r s ṇ ḍ	s , , ,
Rāravēṇu	s , , r	g , p ,	d , ś ,	n , d ,	p , d p	m g r s	r s ṇ ḍ	s , , ,

⁶ Popley, H A, “Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 4, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz),” *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,

Anupallavi begins on the svara riṣabam. The first bar (i.e. two akṣara-s of ādi tāla) is following the same note. However, the rhythmic pattern is different. It is respectively 3+1 and 2+1+1 “r,,r r,r”.

Viśeṣa prayōgas: rsṇḍ, dṢnd p,dpmgrs, ndpm

3. *Sṛkeṭṭapāviyānēn - Rāga : Kāmbhōdi - Tāla : Miśracāpu - Tonic Note : C*

The notation given by the composer in western system⁷ is given below.

164. சீர்கெட்ட பாலி ஆனேன்

Kambodhi. Tonic C. Chapu.

| த சீ நீ நா | ந நா நா பா | ப நா நா பா | ம கா ரீ சா |
 திரு முத்த நொளி வற்ற பெரு வினை களில் உற்று

| ச ரீ மா கா | பநா நீ நா | பா, ; ; ; ; மடபா||
 சீர் கெட்ட பா வியா னேன் காள்

| த நா சீ சீ | நீ, நா பா | சீ நீ நா பா | ம கா ரீ சா||
 ஒரு முக மாய் உன திடம் மனம் திரும் பிட

| ச ரீ மா கா | ரீ சா கா ரீ | சா, ; ; ; ; ||
 ஊக்கம் அருள் பரணே - -

Meaning

Due to the wicked deeds, the sacredness became dim in radiance. I am wholly a sinful being.

Yet, at last, my soul is drawn towards you, inspired by your grace.

⁷ Popley, H A, “Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 2, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz),” *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,

Musical aspect

This song commences with the phrase ‘dṣ, n, d,’. This phrase can convey the identity of the raga Kāmbhōdi. The following phrase ‘dd,d,p,’ has the jaṅṭaprayōga. viśēṣaprayōga like ‘pd, n, d,’ ‘sr, m, g,’ are used.

In this phrase ‘pd, n, d,’ the svāra ‘n’ is sounding like ‘śn’. Here ‘ś’ is anusvara. Then comes the svāra ‘p’. The second line also begins with the svāra ‘d’. The phrase ‘ś, n, d,’ is repeating three times in the pallavi. And the first line ending the svāra ‘p’ the second line ending in the svāra ‘s’. ‘d’ is the dominating note in this song.

1 st	dṣ, n, d,	dd, d, p,	pd, d, p,	mg, r, s,	sr, m, g,	pd, n, d,	p,, ,, ,,	,,, m, p,
2 nd	dd, ś, ś,	n,, d, p,	śn, d, p,	mg, r, s,	sr, m, g,	rs, g, r,	S,, ,, ,,	,,, ,, ,,

Tāla aspect

Each syllable of the svāra comes on the beat, so that the song can be easily sung in the other tāla like caturaśrajātītripuṭa and tīśratripuṭa. For example, the same song applies in caturaśrajātītripuṭa tāla,

	X	1	2	3	X	V	X	V
1 st	d ś n d	d d d p	p d d p	m g r s	s r m g	p d n d	p , , , , m	p
	Tirumuga	Thoilvatru	Peruvinaī	Kalilutru	sīrkeṭṭa	pā viyā	Nēn	nā n
2 nd	d d ś ś	n , d p	ś n d p	m g r s	s r m g	r s g r	s , , , , ,	, , , ,
	Orumugha	māy u na	Tidomanam	tirumpiḍa	ūkkama	ruḷpara	Nē	

Literary Elements

The songs are concise with simple structure, classical use of language, poetic imagery, and thematic characteristics which are impactful for the community of the followers. There are rhyming words observed in the literature of the songs for example “Dvithīyākṣaraprāsa”

or two syllable words that are rhyming with each other. For example the first line begins with the word ‘TiruMugha’ (The Holy face) and the second line begins with the word ‘OruMugha’ (The one face). The lyrics are in Tamil language and based on the Christian theme.

4. Immattumjīvantandakarta - Rāga: Ānandabhairavi - Tāla: Ādi - Tonic Note: C

The notation documented by the composer in western system⁸ is given below.

363. இம்மட்டும் ஜீவந்தந்த கர்த்தா

Ānandabhairavi. *Ādi.*

Tonic C.

Pal. | பா ப ப நீ த ப ம | க ம ப ம | க க ரி ச |
 இம் மட்டும் ஜீவன் தந்த கர்த்தா வை அத்தி யந் த

Fin.

| கா ரி ச க ரி க ம | ப ம கா | ரி சா ||
 கான் ன மய க்ஷேத்தி ரிபுரே மர ச

Musical aspect

The grāhasvara of this song is ‘p’. ‘p’ is the sustaining note in the first tālavattā. All svāra-s come only in the beat. In the phrase ‘n d p m’, ‘n’ is more stressed than the other note, and followed by the phrase ‘g m p m’. The svāra ‘g’ originates from ‘s’ and follows ‘m p m’. The melody is progressing through the jaṅṭaprayōga in the svāra ‘g’ to end in ‘s’. The composer uses simple form of melody in the tālādi. The pallavi is ending with the note ‘s’.

⁸ Popley, H A, “Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 4, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz),” *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,

Anu. | பா ப ப ச் ச் ச் ச் | நீ ச் ரீ | ச்⁹நீ ச் ச் |
நம் மை ரட் சிக் க வந்து நம் மை ப லி யாய்த் தந்து

D. C.
பா ச் ச் நீ த ப | மா ப ம | க ரி க ம |
நற் சுகம் மே வ வும் அற் பு த மா க வும்

Anupallavi begins with the svara ‘p’. Even in the first āvartana the composer himself uses only one svara ‘p’, and the next āvartana sustain the svara ‘ś’. The svara ‘ś’ is dominating in this line. ‘śn, ś, ś,’ is rare phrase in this rāga. The jaṅṭaprayōga in the svara ‘ś’ is used four times even in this section. ‘m,, p, m, gr, g, m,’ is viśēṣaprayōga in this rāga.

Cha. | பா ப ப பந் ப ம | க ம ப ம | க க ரி ச் ||
கா லஞ் சொல் போல்க ழியும் தண் ணீரைப் போல் வடியும்

கா ரி ச் க ரி க ம | ப ம க ரி | சா ; |
க னுவைப் போ லே யும் ஓ ழி யும்

Then caraṇa commences with the svara ‘p’ and the first line of the caraṇa is highly similar to the pallavi. The svara-s ‘p’ and ‘n’ are the only differences from those phrases. The similar portions are mentioned in the bold.

	T	1	2	3	T	V	T	V
P	p , p p	n d p m	g m p m	g g r s	g , r s	g r g m	p m g r	S
C	p , p p	p np m	g m p m	g g r s	g , r s	g r g m	p m g r	S

The later portion of melody is also following the same pattern. In the phrase ‘p, d p p n, d p m’ the svara ‘d’ is stressed and the melody followed by the viśeṣaprayōga in the rāga ‘gm, p, m, g, r, r, s.’. The next melody portion is also a repeat like the melody of pallavi. The composer has purposefully connected all the songs with pallavi and anupallavi. Then, the last line of the caraṇa is also a reflection of the anupallavi. And the last four āvartana-s are making double speed in the melody. The similar portions are mentioned in the bold.

	T	1	2	3	T	V	T	V
A	p ,	p p	ś ś	ś ś	n ,	ś r̄	ś n	ś ś
C	p ,	p p	ś ś	ś ś	r̄ r̄	ś r̄	ś n	ś ś

The meaning of this song is ‘I am very close to you’. As a devotee requests God for the blessings. It shows the relation between God and the people.

The scopes for furthers works of documenting

Even though the Karnāṭaka Music notation system restricts the universal access as it relies heavily on vernacular language, making it challenging for musicians who are oblivious to this notation system, the compositions of H. A. Popley may be notated in Karnāṭaka system for future archival use. “Western Music cannot open the doors of the Indian heart...”⁹ as it falls short in notation Indian Music primarily due to the intricate and diverse gamaka varieties present in Indian Musical Traditions. The nuanced embellishments that are present, especially in Karnāṭaka compositions, are difficult to accurately represent within the constraints of western notation system.

The human voice and mind can possess and express emotion, convey subtle nuances, and interpret cultural contexts and create new concepts through music which notation, be it of any musical system, fails to express. The notation may not be able to carry the richness and depth of the organic musical concept substantiated by cultural identity which can be expressed through subtle variations in rhythm and phrasing that are intrinsic to humanistic musical expression. Therefore, digital audio archives may be necessary to fill this gap.

Conclusion

Innovative documentation plays a crucial role in preserving cultural heritage for future generations, ensuring accessibility and understanding of its richness. As a vital part of history, documentation serves as a testament to the evolution and intricates of societies and their cultural expressions. It also serves as a tribute to the real authors behind the narratives, acknowledging their contributions and preserving their legacies.

⁹ Popley, H A, *The Musical heritage in Evangelism*, page226

H. A. Popley had approached with the long vision in his musical works which can be carried forward by initiates to documenting and preserving them. Furthermore, audio recording, once available to the people under the cultural community for public interest, the composition may renew and echo in the wall and in and around the Indian churches, especially in south India. Music can be understood as an experience or art of life for those who cherish or nourish their interest in it. In that sense, the Karnāṭaka Christian compositions of H. A. Popley are unique in nature.

Yet, more has to be studied to determine the life of H. A. Popley and other pioneers of Karnāṭaka music. This paper has taken up a small part of his compositions, and it opens further scope for research exploration for the future.

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Reference

1. "Leaders, Christian." Encyclopedia of India. . Encyclopedia.com. 21 Feb. 2024
<https://www.encyclopedia.com>
2. H. A. Popley. The Music of India. Calcutta: Association press, 1921.
3. Popley, H A. The Sacred Kural, or the Tamil Veda of Tiruvalluvar. New Delhi: Abhijeet Publication, 1931.
4. Stephen L.I. and Popley H.A., Handbook of Musical Evangelism. Madras: Methodist publishing house,1914.
5. Popley, H A. "Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 2, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz)," *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,
6. Popley, H A. "Tune Book to Tamil Christian Lyrics, Part 4, by H A Popley (English and Tamiz)," *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed February 25, 2024,
7. Popley, H A. "The Musical Heritage of India." International Review of Mission 10 (1921): 223-235.